

Embedded Linux Boot Sequence Design

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Abstract

This article helps you to understand how Linux embedded product will boot, what are booting stages, what is design root cause for two stage boot loaders (u-Boot and MLO). The design of the boot code is the essential technology and a crucial step in the system development process for Linux embedded systems because it is located at the bottom of the device. The target audience should have knowledge and understanding of processor, controller, different types of memory and should be Linux background. In this article, a use case example for a two stage boot loader is provided to help readers understand when to utilize one.

Keywords: Memory Loader (MLO), Universal Boot Loader (u-Boot), System-On-Chip (SoC), Main Stack Pointer (MSP)

1. Introduction

When we turn on or reset any Linux device, internally many firmware code will get executes till application launches. Initial part of firmware code is design and developed by SoC manufacturer and later part of firmware code design and developed by vendors as they need. This article explains you design of firmware code of both SoC and vendor.

2. Literature survey

There are numerous literatures in academia which have performed research and development on the u-Boot. In [1], the discussion is done on the difficulty in understanding the u-Boot porting, as well as the difficulty associated with achieving the normal bootup of the kernel. Work on transplantation of u-Boot is done in [2] which emphasized the retrieval of the OS kernel, transplanting and creation of a custom build of the operating system suitable for a given board. The authors of [3] discussed about various methods to boot an all-programmable SoC over the PCI Express Link medium. The requirement to optimize the normal boot time consumption by the u-Boot program is analyzed and shown in [4] for the Android Operating System (AOS). An interesting work on the development of solution to perform the production-level testing of the hardware using the bootloader is presented in [5]. The article [6] talks about various trusted devices involved in an Embedded Linux based device, which again involves the discussion on the

bootloader program, and the utilization of u-Boot and the Linux kernel to design peripheral drivers such as UART and GPIOs for LEDs is discussed in [7].

Hence, from the discussion done in the above paragraph, it is clear and evident that a sound knowledge in the bootloader process in Embedded Linux based SoC systems is vital for multiple applications in the domain of Embedded systems. With this thought, this paper brings forth a detailed discussion on the Embedded Linux Bootloader design process, which primarily aims to serve anyone who wishes to work efficiently with the bootloader program as well as conduct important research and development.

3. What is booting?

The process of starting a device or computer through an equipment button is known as booting. When a device is turned on, the computer chip has nothing in its main memory, so some cycle must stack programming into memory before it usually executes. This can be accomplished via a distinct system process as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Boot process [8]

3.1 Booting from SoC

SoC contains ROM and small size static RAM.

Figure 2 Vector Table [9]

As shown in Fig. 2, when turn on device or reset device,

1. Initially program counter PC is loaded with the address 0x00000000.
2. Next the processor fetches the value at 0x00000000 into the MSP. Initial value of MSP is 0x20008000, here processor first initializes Main Stack Pointer and its programmer’s responsibility to put the valid value at the location 0x00000000 (Usually taken care by the startup code).
3. Next the processor reads the address of the reset handler (reset vector) from the location 0x00000004 into the Program Counter. It is very important to store the address of reset handler in the location 0x00000004. In reset vector, manufacturer already preprogrammed in this address.
4. At last processor jumps to reset handler or reset vector and start executing the first instruction which programmer wrote there. Generally, reset vector exists SoC ROM boot loader code and from here ROM boot loader starts executes.

3.2 Design flow of SoC ROM Boot Loader (RBL) init

- 1) System initialization
- 2) Setup the stack
- 3) Setup the watch Dog Timer (WDT)
- 4) Configure the system clock
- 5) Booting

Figure 3. ROM code start up sequence [10]

As given in [10] when system starts up, basic initialization happens and in routine stack will setup then set up watchdog timer (WDT), here WDT is set to 3 minutes, within 3 min RBL code has to detect boot device (boot device can be USB drive, MMC/SD, network) by reading sysboot pin otherwise it will reset again and performs system clock configuration and finally it will jumps to booting first stage boot loader as depicted in Fig. 3.

4. Booting

Fig. 4 shows the booting system. As given in [10] initially a booting device list is created. The list comprises of all devices which will be looked for a booting image. Based on the SYSBOOT, the list is filled up.

When the booting device list is set up, the booting routine analyzes the devices enumerated in the list consecutively and either executes the memory booting or peripheral booting technique relying upon the booting device type. The peripheral

booting is executed while the booting device type is USB, Ethernet or UART. The memory booting system is executed while the booting device type is one of NAND, MMC, NOR or SPI-EEPROM. The memory booting system reads information from a memory type device. In the event that a substantial booting image is found and effectively read from the external memory device, the code starts to execute.

Figure 4. Booting (source [10])

The peripheral booting method downloads software data from Host (normally a PC) to the device through UART / Ethernet links. The ROM code utilizes a host-slave protocol for synchronization. Upon fruitful USB, UART or Ethernet connection the host sends the binary image data.

4.1 Peripheral Booting

As given in [10] ROM code can boot from one of below three unique peripheral interfaces:

- EMAC: 10/100/1000 Mbps Ethernet utilizing standard TCP/IP network boot protocol TFTP and BOOTP
- USB: Client mode, full speed,
- UART: 115.2Kbps, no parity, 1 stop bit, 8 bits, no flow control

The reason for peripheral interface booting is to download a boot image from an outside have (commonly a PC). This booting technique is for the most part utilized for programming flash memories associated with the device ex: firmware update, initial flashing. Boot image is directly downloaded into internal RAM at some location on device as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Peripheral Boot method flow [10]

4.2 Memory Booting

Figure 6. Memory Booting [10]

As shown in Fig. 6, ROM code endeavors to initialize the memory device or card associated on MMC interface. If neither card nor memory device is discovered, the ROM code carries on to the subsequent booting device. The standard ID cycle and Relative Card Address (RCA) task are utilized. The ROM code, however, makes the assumption that there is only one memory or card on the bus. The data in a MMC/SD card might be formatted as FAT file system or raw binary. ROM code reads the booting file within file system or raw sectors from image and boots from it.

Raw Mode: The booting image in raw mode can be found in one of the four successive places in the main area.: offset 0x0 / 0x20000 (128KB) / 0x40000 (256KB) / 0x60000 (384KB). Therefore, a booting image must not be larger than 128KB in size. However, starting at one of the above-mentioned locations, a device can be flashed with an image larger than 128KB. hence, the ROM code does not verify the image size. The image will cross the next image boundary, which is the only drawback.

FAT Mode: SD/MMC card holds a FAT file system so ROM code is able to read and process. The binary image utilized by the booting system is taken from a particular booting file named "MLO". This MLO file must be situated in the partition of type FAT32.

In this article I am considering memory booting i.e., boot device is MMC/SD card. MMC/SD card need to done two partitions.

1. FAT: MLO, u-boot, zImage, dtb, uEnv.txt
2. EXT: Root File System (RFS)

RBL copies first stage boot loader i.e., MLO from SD card to internal static RAM (128 KB)of SoC and passes control to it.

MLO: First stage boot loader

- Initialization
- configure RAM controller

MLO copies second stage boot loader i.e., u-Boot from SD card to external RAM and passes control to it.

u-Boot: Second stage boot loader

Second stage boot loader copies uEnv.txt file to external RAM, it contains environment variable then reads its configuration settings, searches and loads linux kernel image i.e., zImage and device tree binary i.e., dtb image into external RAM. Then sets up kernel boot args and passes control to kernel which utilizes boot args and device tree address to initializes itself and devices.

Linux Kernel

- Linux kernel initialize hardware components and using boot args locate and mount root file system.
- Linux kernel runs init process to start user space. The init process now spawns other user space process based on its configuration file.
- Init is first process in Linux system and it's PID is 0.

Init

- It will see at the /etc/inittab file to conclude the Linux run level
- Run level available as below
0-stop / halt

- 1-One / Single user mode
- 2-More than one user i.e., multiuser mode with no NFS
- 3-More than one user (Multiple user) mode under the command line interface and no under the GUI.
- 4-unused
- 5-More than one user (Multiple user) mode under GUI i.e., the standard run level for most of the Linux based systems (x11)
- 6-restart / reboot

In Linux default run level is 5. Starts executions rc5.d startup scripts from /etc, here onwards application starts.

Entire boot flow process can be seen in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Entire boot process flow (source [8])

Why do we need two stage boot loaders?

As given in [8] SoC designers companies, during SoC design they don't have enough information about

- What is external hardware which connects to their SoC, so difficult to initialize that hardware during SoC ROM Boot loader execution.
- SoC designers don't know about external RAM and its size so can't initialize and configure. Different vendors have different hardware as per their requirements and as per their hardware, software size will get differ (MLO, u-Boot, kernel and dtb)
- As per their software size, these vendors will design/decide RAM size so MLO software written by these vendors because they know RAM size/RAM controller

information so MLO can easily initialize and configure RAM controller, that's why first stage boot loader required and also u-Boot can't fit in internal RAM of SoC because of its size.

- u-Boot knows information about external hardware which connects to SoC or communicates with SoC.

Use case example

- Mobile 1. Only front camera, Bluetooth, single SIM, small display, 2GB RAM.
- Mobile 2. Front and back camera, Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, dual sim, big display, 4GB RAM.

As explained above, SoC designer not aware about these vendors hardware and RAM size, which are going connect with their SoC. All above two handsets can have common SoC.

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